

REAL TIME SIMULATION OF DIABETES CREATION EFFECTS AND IMPACTS ON MAN'S ACTIVITIES AT KUKURANTUMI IN THE EASTERN REGION OF GHANA

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes is a pathetic illness or disease that affects man in various ways. If untreated or well catered for leads to negative effects or impacts on the body including unto death. This research paper sorts to investigate other negative impacts of untreated diabetes on personal grounds as simulated at Kukurantumi in the Eastern Region of Ghana. It is found that untreated or unattended diabetes leads to wide spread of damages in the body including damage to organs, nerves, blood vessels etc. This reduces rate of sugar breakdown leading to no bowels formation in the body, hard faeces or stools, running stomach etc. Occultic world generation of illness and diseases such as diabetes also gave a nice result as that part of the research was also accessed. Hard work, walking several kilometers per day should result in high rate of absorption and glucose breakdown in the body. But this isn't so as sugar illness or diabetes creation effects from another world or occultic world does not believe in the learning, philosophy or glucose breakdown during exercises, hard work, playing football or covering several kilometers per day through walking. This occultic philosophical world believes in no work done but getting or generating results. They just eat all the sugars with possibility of enjoying one milo tin, three milks coupled with sugar on daily basis and releasing the sugar content or glucose build up in their body through transmission lines or links like penis or vagina (spiritual inclination) into other people (people from another philosophical world) body or accounts on daily basis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ancient scientific evidence and an increase in epidemiological facts suggest that “healthy eating habits and moderate exercise can reduce the incidence of heart attacks, diabetes and non-communicable diseases” (WHO, 2002). This is true to an extent and

at the same time questionable as research and investigations has proven otherwise. All sickness has a founding occultic or human creation basis before installing into the world for World Health Organization to work on it as United Nations Problem or World Bank problem.

Received: 18 March 2026

Revised: 21 March 2026

Accepted: 25 March 2026

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26643/ijr/46>

Once this happens, various health institutions including the hospitals becomes the workers to work on it on daily basis for the goodwill of another world or occultic world against another. And diabetes is no exception as its main cause is from food. So imagine one realm or world not interested in your eating habits and hence wants you to stop eating, *diabetes creation and its impacts is the case to deal with here*. Diabetes has positive impacts and at the same time negative repercussions when untreated well or unattended to in life. Diabetes mellitus, characterized by chronic high blood sugar after taking too much food (from one school of thought) or when a lot of sugar has been released into your account (body) through transmission lines including the penis or vagina (another school of thought), severely impacts health by causing widespread damage to a lot of body parts. Some of the body parts includes damages to organs, nerves, brain and blood vessels. Uncontrolled diabetes leads to complications including kidney disease, retinopathy, heart disease, stroke, and amputations due to poor circulation of blood and glucose in the body. Effective management requires lifestyle changes, blood sugar monitoring, and sometimes medication and exercise. All these recommendations or healing parameters are basically based on schools of thought or diabetes creation world and impacts. As application of one school of thought healing strategy when it comes to source of diabetes or type of diabetes (Type 1 or Type 2) will not be applicable in another school of thought (occultic realm) operation. Realm operation and salvation work is for all but not unto all. As once salvation work generating Billions of Pounds Sterling's into personal accounts on monthly basis will be serving as a destruction work on monthly basis as the world or realm losses Billions of Pounds Sterling's into another realms or school of thoughts accounts. In a nut shell, what is salvation unto another realm might or is a destruction gospel message unto another world and hence the creation of some hospitals as prison zones to address or solve cases. This is a justification for the use of the word 'cases' in hospitals or some hospitals as used in the police services or security services.

2 DIABETES AMONG HUMANS AND ITS ASSESSMENT

2.1 EFFECTS OF DIABETICS IN THE BODY

Health effects and complications when talking about diabetes is very pitiful. Some of the common symptoms associated with diabetes includes frequent urination (polyuria), extreme thirst and hunger for water (polydipsia), severe or uncontrolled hunger for food, and unexplained weight loss are common, especially in Type 1 diabetes. Bitter mouth and no appetite for food and water is another severe symptoms and this is when the sugar or glucose level in the body is around 26mmol/L as recorded during research. The frequent urination has a physical and spiritual implication before a diabetic patient even pees or urinates at any point in time as the frequent urination are all transmission links related (penis or vagina issue).

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Accepted: 25 March 2026

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26643/ijr/46>

Other negative effects of having diabetes also include cardiovascular damages. Diabetes significantly increases the risk of stroke and heart attack, with diabetics 2 – 4 times more likely to experience these severe events in once life. Kidney disease (Diabetic Nephropathy) is also another illness that is a leading cause of kidney failure, accounting for high rates of end-stage renal disease. Nerve damages (Neuropathy) resulting in numbness, pain, and weakness occur especially in the feet, which increases injury risk and reduces healing, sometimes leading to amputation and possibly stroke. Continuous subjecting of once body to high sugar through transmission links or staying with people or someone who is always eating sugary food is a very dangerous thing. One ought to observe his/her environment or home and if possible, relocate or report individuals who are into high sugar foods intake and not being affected with sugar/diabetes to health assistant/professionals or health investigators for observation and assessment. This will help control their sugar levels at any point in time. This is because one might be going through and practicing all the protocols when talking about controlling diabetes or sugar level in the body. But someone living around or in the home and taking high volume of food or sugar foods might be releasing the sugar into once account or body on daily basis. Such a person will be reporting at health facilities on weekly basis with high sugar levels or values in terms of checking sugar at the hospital. But will not have or see a defined reason for the high glucose or sugar levels in the body. Vision Loss (Retinopathy) is another negative impact of High blood sugar in the body. It leads to damages vessels in the eye, causing blurred vision or blindness. Wound healing and infection is another negative creation effects from high sugar or glucose levels in the body. Poor circulation and weakened immune response leads to slow healing and frequent infections, such as urinary or skin infections. The skin always heals itself once there is a cut or wound. Its all about dead cells dying and new cells regenerating to cause healings on the skin or body. But once there is no good blood flow as life is in the blood, blood with adequate nutrients, the new cells formation and resultant healing of wounds becomes problematic. High blood sugar results in bitter saliva and uneasy stomach to the extent that swallowing saliva becomes very difficult.

2.2 BLOOD AND IMPACTS ON DIABETES

Blood is a specialized bodily fluid that transports oxygen, nutrients, hormones, and waste products throughout the body. It makes up roughly 7 - 8% of human body weight and consists of four main components consisting of red blood cells, white blood cells, platelets, and plasma. The plasma is a yellowish liquid comprising about 55% of blood volume, composed of water, proteins, and salts. Red Blood Cells (Erythrocytes) is composed of haemoglobin, which carries oxygen from the lungs to tissues in the body. The White Blood Cells (Leukocytes) fights infections and defend the body against foreign invaders or pathogens. Platelets

(Thrombocytes) are the tiny cells that assist in blood clotting, repairing damage to vessels. The human blood has the following functions in the body; for the purpose of transport in the body? It delivers nutrients and oxygen to cells while removing waste products. For the purpose of blood serving as a defensive component in the body? It is mainly responsible for transporting white blood cells and antibodies to fight diseases. It's one of the body fluids responsible for regulation of temperature in the body. It helps in managing or regulating body temperature, pH balance, and fluid volume in the body.

One negative effect of diabetes is wound creation and its healings on the skin or body. Wound healing is a complex, dynamic process supported by a myriad of cellular events that must be tightly coordinated to efficiently repair damaged tissue. Derangement in wound-linked cellular behaviours, as occurs with diabetes and ageing, can lead to healing impairment and the formation of chronic, non-healing wounds (Wilkinson et al., 2020). These wounds are a significant socioeconomic burden due to their high prevalence and recurrence. Thus, there is an urgent requirement for the improved biological and clinical understanding of the mechanisms that underpin wound repair. Here, we review the cellular basis of tissue repair and discuss how current and emerging understanding of wound pathology could inform future development of efficacious wound therapies (Wilkinson et al., 2020). Our skin is specialized to interface with the external environment and provides a variety of important homeostatic functions, from regulating thermostability to sensing extrinsic stimuli. Crucially, the skin acts as a primary defence barrier, preventing desiccation and mechanical, chemical, thermal and photic damage to internal structures (Takeo et al., 2015; Wilkinson et al., 2020). This defence extends to a sophisticated immune barrier response that protects against pathogenic infection, while supporting microorganisms via an elegantly adapted host–microbiota axis (Naik S, et al. 2015; Wilkinson et al., 2020). The skin has also evolved efficient and rapid mechanisms to close breaches to its barrier in a process collectively known as the wound healing response. Wound repair is classically simplified into four main phases: haemostasis, inflammation, proliferation and dermal remodelling (Broughton et. al., 2006; Wilkinson et al., 2020). The blood is an important parameter when dealing with diabetes, sugar or glucose levels among sugar patients. Whenever a doctor is dealing with the transports of oxygen, minerals, nutrients, removal of waste products in the life of a patient, the bloods is the main parameter to consider.

Fig 1: Diabetes and wound repair (Source: Wilkinson et. al., 2020)

Diabetes impairs wound repairs and healing due to high blood sugar damaging blood vessels, nerves, and immune systems leading to slow recovery as a diabetic patient. Skin recovery requires daily checks, significant glucose management and specialized wound care to prevent serious tissues damages.

3 RESEARCH AREA

The research areas focus at Diabetes creation effects and treatment at Koforidua Regional Hospital and Kukurantumi Community Hospital all in the Eastern Region of Ghana. But the main point of call for this diabetes investigation and research is at Kukurantumi community hospital at Kukurantumi which is part of the Abuakwa North Constituency. Kukurantumi is the district capital of the Abuakwa North constituency in the Eastern Region of Ghana as depicted in **Fig 2**. Activities in the district includes all kinds of government institutions operations and management of the district and its resources, businesses involved in trading (buying and selling), farming activities etc. It is notable for her Ofori Panin Senior High School and its contribution towards human gold production in the community, Ghana and worldwide. The secondary school has served the community for several years and is notable for her contribution in shaping and moulding human gold products with basics and foundations in education theories and principles. The community is a peaceful one compared to other

communities or towns in the eastern region notable for big weekly market days activities where traders travel several miles and kilometres for buying and selling activities.

Fig 2: District Map of Abuakwa North Municipal

4 IMPACTS OF DIABETES ON MAN'S ACTIVITIES AND MANAGEMENT INTELLIGENCE

4.1 Impacts of Diabetes on Mans activities

What is salvation unto another, a world or another school of thought is a destruction unto another school of thought, a world or realm. The discovery or creation of diabetes as an illness or sickness possibly is salvation sickness unto a world whiles it is a destruction to the lives and destinies of another world or realm or school of thought. By this declaration, the discovery of diabetes or creation of diabetes is causing havoc and generating Billions of Pounds Sterling's from a world, country, realm, people into another worlds, realm or school of thought which is enriching them on daily basis. Generating sickness such as strokes, numbness, heart problems, sore throats, frequent urination, prevention from eating good/sweet foods, dehydration of the body etc generates Billions of Pounds Sterling's into a hospital account which belongs to a school of thought or realm or a body. The sickness listed above are all diabetes sickness associated worldwide. Seeking for once health and wellbeing on daily basis has to do with paying all the bills in the house including hospital bills for once health and independence. And all the money's generated here ends in the occultic world or school of thought or realms account.

Generating numbness as a sickness including frequent urination or dehydration is occultic realm operation effects from a well calculated or programmed adventure against a rich man or rich world. Based on research and investigations, diabetes or sugar sickness is manhood (penis) or womanhood (vagina) associated or registered. Everything about the sickness is

either about the penis for men or vagina for women. The principal agenda in the diabetes generating process is deleting once greatness, hard work, strength or ability or manhood or womanhood. So the principal target is the penis in men and vagina in women. The target group of individuals here are people who have worked hard and there is Billions of Pounds sterling's or dollars in their account but not accessed physically for the normal eye to see. The occultic world or people targets their rich resources, picks their things or items, wears their expensive cloths, watches, items in the absence or when the rich man or individual is gone to work and even sleeps or have sexual intercourse in their homes and houses. Imagine operating a realm which involves having sexual intercourse over the wealth that has been made and taking total control over affairs? Haven't one taking the manhood or womanhood in an individual? *Once they do this, then man's penis or vagina has been taken over with the final verdict of you not being the owner or the creator or even the one who worked so hard for the wealth or property. Once this take over happens, then there is continuous pricking of the penis at any advantageous point resulting in frequent urination or resultant dehydration. The pricking is done by the penis or vagina of everyone associated with the take-over. That is spiritually, ethnically, as an occultic group, as a hospital group etc working unto salvation (money generation unto greatness and riches in life). This is done together with continuous release of sugar into that person's system. This leads to dehydration of the body and increase in sugar level and hence resultant diabetes. The dehydration process for the sugar victim or affected or patients also goes with associated penis enlargement or elongation in favour of the world which created the sugar sickness - diabetes.*

On the issue of numbness, the creators of the illness also accesses your resources or your homes in an intelligent way. As the fucking or sleeping in your home/house continues, there is continuous touching of items that your hands accesses in the homes on daily basis or helping you generate a wealthy world. Some of the items includes phones, laptops, TV remotes, handkerchiefs, boxers, panties, office chairs or desks, doors, shovels, screw drivers, pliers, favourite pens and pencils, working tools etc. They occultically generates strength into their hands and realms whiles relinquishing weakness and pain in every regards into your hands and by that resultant destruction to once hands, legs, feet's etc. Through occultic means and spiritual realm operations, they fuck you (sleeps with your penis) using your legs, hands, feet and penis and that generates all kinds of repercussions against you as an individual. They sexually takes the penis and vagina, takes the manhood or womanhood and with no desire in you for sexual interactions. This is what leads to numbness, weak in legs, weak in bones and body leading to strokes and all kinds of health issues or consequences. And hence the number of associated health complications when dealing or taking about diabetes worldwide.

Research findings and investigations indicates that some even drink all the alcoholic drinks and eat all the sugar foods but never registers high sugar levels on the Glucometer. This is simply because, they make use of all transmission links and networks intelligence such as through the penis or vagina and lands all the sugar taken inside the body of people they are not unto salvation works with.

The impacts of diabetes on man is terrible as it leaves him in a state of strokes with no one to help, numbness with inability to work and cater for once self, growing lean, bladder issues, draining of intelligence and unable body and brain coordination towards personal satisfaction and advancement in life. In some cases, wealth and money worked for are used to cater for diabetic patients which is losing of resources and resultant generation of wealth into other realms or schools of thoughts accounts. The final verdict in this case is death when all the draining in terms of wealth, intelligence, human resources such as skin, colour, body, feet's, back heels have been pushed into another world or realm. In finality, a well lived life full of intelligence, beauty and wealth is released to another world or realm. So one can see sugar patients legs being ugly and of different colours, swollen faces, sour or bitter mouth, redefined faces, change in facial patterns etc.

4.2 Diabetes Key Management Strategies

Management of diabetes is highly dependent of how one acquired the diabetes based on the concept of high food (carbohydrates) intake resulting in high glucose (sugar levels) in the body and hence the resultant diabetes. This is from once school of thought. Or from occultic realm manipulation and sickness creation which also has the associated sugar or glucose build up in the body. This is also from another school of thought. Based on these perspectives, one healing or diabetes management strategy may be applicable for one school of thought and might not be applicable for another realms sugar operations and management when talking about healings. On need to observe his environment, eating habit and way of life or activities and adapt the most appropriate and applicable diabetes management strategies or principles. Some of the strategies are elaborated below and are applicable based on how one acquired the sugar or diabetes sickness in life;

- **Healthy Foods Eating:** One needs to focus on high-fibre foods, vegetables, eat proteins, and healthy fats. Limit sugar-sweetened beverages, processed snacks, and saturated fats. People who finds themselves in diabetes sickness world are possibly sugar eating foods lovers or ate too much foods (carbohydrates). So it's very difficult to do away with sugary foods. The only option here is not to eat sugar foods too much and the

need to go with a sugar eating controlling system. That is once a while in the course of the month you eat a little sugar while still monitoring and controlling the diabetes or sugar levels in the body. Adhering to a balanced diet to manage carbohydrates calorie intake is very important as it plays great role in the diabetes illness healing process and management strategies.

- Physical Activities or getting involved in work on daily basis. Regular exercise, including at least 150 minutes of moderate aerobic activity and strength training weekly, helps control blood sugar. Work is done when a force moves through a distance in the direction of the force. The possibility of walking several kilometres per day also reduces glucose or sugar level in the body and hence avoiding diabetes in the body (a school of thought). As one walks, there is burning of all glucose in the food that one has eating instead of a build-up of glucose or sugar in the body. Continuous building of sugar without breaking of glucose when work is done is the reason for high sugar values in the body after pricking the finger and checking the sugar level with the glucometer.
- Weight Management: Losing 5 – 7% of body weight can significantly improve insulin sensitivity, particularly for Type 2 diabetes. Weight management is very necessary as it also gives the opportunity for good blood flows in the body.
- Medication is one of the ultimate management tools when one has been infected with the diabetes illness. The diabetes Type 1 requires insulin therapy for survival. Diabetes Type 2 is often managed with oral medications (e.g., Metformin, Diabenil, SGLT-2 inhibitors) and may require insulin when the sugar level in the body is very high and needs to be reduced drastically in order to save the sugar affected patient.
- Monitoring Blood Sugar using a Glucometer or continuous glucose monitor (CGM) to track levels, with a typical target A1C below 53 mmol/L (7%). Coupling this with education and Support helps one to manage diabetes and lives for longer years within the community or society. This can be done by utilizing Diabetes Self-Management Education and Support (DSMES) services and hospital services in the community or country.
- Lifestyle Factors is also one important parameter in the management and control of sugar levels in once life. Getting sufficient or enough sleep ranging between 7hours - 8hours per day and managing stress (through relaxation techniques) are crucial, as stress can raise blood glucose levels in the body on daily basis. And continuous stress will yield a resultant high blood sugar levels in the body over time.

- Since diabetes is spiritually inclined or realm operation associated or occultic realm operations, manipulated and generated as established through research and investigations, fighting against all odds also increases once survival on planet earth the very moment he/she is generated as a diabetic patient.

Table 1: Glucometer Sugar Readings as Recorded at Koforidua and Kukurantumi Community Hospital in the Eastern Region of Ghana

Readings/ Recordings №	Koforidua Hospital (mmol/L)	Kukurantumi Hospitals (mmol/L)
R1	18.8	26.0
R2	17.6	25.5
R3	15.7	23.7
R4	12.1	23.2
R5	11.8	20.0
R6	10.9	18.6
R7	10.7	16.9
R8	10.6	16.7
R9	10.6	14.1
R10	10.5	12.2
R11	10.4	10.3
R12	10.0	9.70
R13	9.80	8.10
R14	8.80	7.80
R15	8.40	7.40
R16	6.80	7.10
R17	5.9	6.1

Table 1 gives a clear indication of Glucometer readings during the research phases. This is during real time research and investigations at the study areas where researcher goes through process of high sugar or glucose levels in body as recorded by Glucometer and hence the need to work on it to bring it to acceptable values (4.0mmol/L – 5.4mmol/L). Patients who records high sugar levels are usually admitted and taken through series of process with continuous monitoring as the patient is worked on to bring his/her sugar level in the body to acceptable values. Some of the activities involved in the healing process includes dieting, hygienic activities, 2hours intervals checking and recordings of sugar levels in the body with Glucometer per day etc. Modern technology and occultic registration and creation also have effects on sugar levels in the lifes of sugar patients. Research findings shows that, some people

use all kinds of creation intelligence and transmission links and lands sugar or glucose amounts in the accounts or bodies of others. In that regard, they do all the heavy carbohydrates and calories consumption resulting in high glucose or sugar registration in their body. But due to creation upon creation and salvation work, where once salvation work is a destruction unto another world or realm, they release all the sugars into once body through transmission links such as the penis and vagina as depicted in **Fig 3** below and recording a high value of 26mmol/L.

Occultic realm generation of such a person as diabetic patient and recording a high sugar level of 30mmol/L for instance is supposed to be on admission for their nurses and doctors to work on. Such a person will leave his or her work which in way will be to her advantage but to the detriment of that occultic world. He or she is therefore to generate money, time and resources in their direction and again to prevent any unforeseen circumstance or bad situation in or against their world.

Fig 2: Sample sugar levels readings by Glucometer

5 CONCLUSION

Activities of man on daily basis towards community, country or world development leads to illness or sickness creation on daily basis. The use of vehicles and the release of exhaust fumes for instance is an example. Job creation and the desire for money and riches also leads to sickness or disease creation and diabetes as a disease is a very good example. This is always done by various schools of thoughts, realm or occultic world registration towards enrichment in life and wealth generation towards salvation work. Whiles causing havoc or damages or destruction to another or other worlds, schools of thoughts or realms. Once a diabetic patient is generated, he is to pay monthly bills at hospitals (salvation work toward enrichment and

greatness of that world or realm) while the patient (human body) is subject to all kinds of inhuman actions (destruction as it's unto losing wealth, money, beauty, intelligence and possibly unto death) in another world. Some of the inhuman activities or sicknesses associated with diabetes includes numbness, stress, dehydration, blindness of the eye, stroke, heart problems, losing of beauty, mental draining out of intelligence to feed another world etc. These are some of the reasons for various complications about diabetes and sugar problems worldwide.

Acknowledgment

I am grateful to the Almighty God for this opportunity and surviving the storms against all odds to write this paper. Grateful I am to Koforidua Regional Hospital and Kukurantumi community Hospital when it comes to having access to the two hospitals facilities for health care and data. I thank my wife, Mrs Rita Abena Darko for the support and encouragement. And to my two sons, Gates and Michael, I say Hurrah and continue to be a blessing unto us all. I thank the Danquah and Gyadu families at Community Four – Nsutam, and the Darko and Kissiwa families at Kukurantumi for their support and hardwork. Finally, I thank the people of Kukurantumi for everything as best known to us all. God bless us all!!

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